

Organic Derivatives of Boron. Part VI. Syntheses of Some Nitrogen-containing Aliphatic Orthoborates

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Reactions of isopropyl borate and ethyl borate with mono- and diethanolamines in various molar ratios yield tris-(2-aminoethyl) borate and tris-(diethanolamine) di(borate) respectively. The mixed alkyl ethanolamine borate derivatives in both cases appear to be unstable and disproportionate readily to give the tris-derivatives. Only phenyl diethanolamine borate could be prepared by the reaction of boric acid with diethanolamine and phenol and its stability, compared to the corresponding alkyl derivatives, may be attributed to internal co-ordination from nitrogen to boron. Diethanolamine hydrogen borate, tris-(2-diethylaminoethyl) borate, and *tritych* boroxazolidine have also been synthesised.

Orthoborate esters have been prepared from lower alkyl borates by employing alcohol-interchange technique by us¹⁻³ and others also⁴⁻⁷. In this communication, an attempt has been made to study the reactions of ethyl and isopropyl borates with some nitrogen-containing mono-, di- and trihydric alcohols (e.g., mono-, di⁸, and triethanolamines and 2-diethylaminoethanol) in different molar ratios and to ascertain the possibility of internal co-ordination from nitrogen to boron in the compounds formed.

Thomas⁷ observed that boric anhydride could not be directly esterified by ethanolamine. He prepared, however, 2-aminoethyl borate by distilling a mixture of ethanolamine and propyl⁹ borate. Salts of boric acid with single or mixed ethanolamines were also reported by Rojhan⁸. The borate of triethanolamine was synthesised from boric acid by Hein and Burkhardt⁹ and Brown and Fletcher¹⁰. Latter workers assigned it the *tritych* structure. Recently, a large number of *tritych* boroxazolidines have been prepared by Weidmann and Zimmerman¹¹ and by Schleppe and Gutsche⁶ either by the alcoholysis of boric acid and mono- and disubstituted boric acid with amino-alcohols or from butyl¹¹ borate by *trans*-esterification.

The reactions between isopropyl borate and monoethanolamine in various molar ratios (1:1 to 1:3) have now been shown to afford tris-(2-aminoethyl) borate quantitatively, based on the ethanolamine taken. No evidence could be found for the formation of mixed esters, 2-aminoethyl di-isopropyl borate (I: R=OPrⁱ) and di-(2-aminoethyl) isopropyl borate which, even formed, disproportionate readily to afford the tris-compound.

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Tris-(2-diethylaminoethyl) borate was also obtained quantitatively by ~~using~~ isopropyl borate to react with 2-diethylaminoethanol in 1:3 molar ratio.

The ready disproportionation of the mixed ester (I: R=OPrⁱ) to give the tris-derivative indicates that in these compounds also, the back co-ordination from alkoxy oxygen to boron¹² is predominant, leaving no possibility for internal co-ordination from nitrogen to boron which could have stabilised the mixed borates. In compounds, where back co-ordination is not prominent, such internal co-ordination does, however, take place, e.g. in 2-aminoethyl diphenyl boronite (I: R=Ph)¹³.

Reactions of ethyl borate with diethanolamine in different stoichiometric ratios (1:1 to 1:3) were also carried out. In each case, the product obtained was tris-(diethanolamine) di(borate) (III). The reaction between isopropyl borate and diethanolamine in equimolar ratio also yielded the same compound.

In view of the ready disproportionation of ethyl or isopropyl diethanolamine borate derivatives in the above reactions, syntheses of higher mixed esters were attempted, taking boric acid as the starting material¹⁴.

Slow distillation of water from an equimolar mixture of boric acid and diethanolamine gave a glassy compound, highly susceptible to hydrolysis, which was found to be diethanolamine hydrogen borate (II: R=OH).

When an equimolar mixture of boric acid, diethanolamine, and an alcohol (cyclohexanol or benzyl alcohol) was refluxed in xylene, followed by the removal of water by distillation with xylene, a colorless semisolid, immiscible with xylene, was obtained which on drying was found to be the hydrogen borate (II, R=OH). When phenol was taken in place of alcohol, phenyl diethanolamine borate (II: R=OPh) was, however, obtained in quantitative yield. This compound is quite stable and can be purified by sublimation.

The hydrolytic stability of diethanolamine aryl boronates (II: R=Ph) has previously been explained by internal co-ordination from nitrogen to boron which has further been confirmed by infrared examinations of these compounds¹⁴. In view of the above,

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13. Letsinger and Skoog, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2491.

14. Musgrave and Park, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1955, 1552.

15. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 203.

in isopropyl diethanolamine borate also, the electrophilic character of the phenyl group appears to be responsible for the decrease in the electron density at the boron atom which, aided with chelation effects, gives rise to the formation of a co-ordinate bond from nitrogen to boron.

When ethyl borate and triethanolamine are mixed in equimolar ratio in benzene, triethyl boroxazolidine is immediately precipitated with evolution of heat. It has been found monomeric in chloroform.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analytical procedures and methods for drying the reagents have been described before¹. The amino-alcohols were fractionated under reduced pressure. Molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in a semimicro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) in chloroform. Melting points were determined in sealed capillary tubes.

Reactions between Isopropyl Borate and Ethanolamine.—Reactions between isopropyl borate and ethanolamine in different ratios were carried out in refluxing benzene. The liberated isopropanol was removed azeotropically. On cooling, the product, tris(2-aminoethyl) borate, solidified in every experiment; m.p. 95-98°, b.p., 92°/0.05 mm. The essential details are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Isopropyl borate (1 <i>M</i>).	Weight of ethanolamine.	Ethanol in azeotrope.	Yield of tris- borate*.	Found (%)**.	
					Boron.	Nitrogen.
1	3.72 g.	3.62 g. (3 <i>M</i>)	3.40 g. (2.86 <i>M</i>)	3.63 g. (95%)	5.60	21.2
2	4.38	2.84 (2 <i>M</i>)	2.80 (2 <i>M</i>)	2.81 (94%)	5.58	21.3
3	5.28	1.71 (1 <i>M</i>)	1.60 (0.95 <i>M</i>)	1.68 (94%)	5.61	21.2

* Based on the quantity of ethanolamine taken.

** Calc. for $B(O\cdot CH_2CH_2NH_2)_3$: B, 5.66; N, 22.0%.

Reaction between Isopropyl Borate and 2-Diethylaminoethanol (Molar Ratio 1:3).—A mixture of diethylaminoethanol (6.2 g., 3 *M*) and isopropyl borate (3.32 g., 1 *M*) in benzene (40 g.) was refluxed for 2 hours and then fractionated. Isopropanol (3.1 g., 3 moles require 3.18 g.) was obtained in the azeotrope. After distilling excess of benzene, the product was distilled under reduced pressure. Tris-(2-diethylaminoethyl) borate (6.0 g.), a colorless heavy liquid, was obtained at 140°/0.6 mm. (Found: B, 2.9; N, 11.6. $C_{12}H_{24}O_3N_3B$ requires B, 3.0; N, 11.8%).

Reactions between Alkyl Borates and Diethanolamine.—Reactions between ethyl or isopropyl borate and diethanolamine were also carried out in refluxing benzene. The liberat-

ed alcohol was fractionated azeotropically. In each experiment, a colorless heavy liquid, immiscible with benzene, was obtained which on drying under reduced pressure yielded tris-(diethanolamine) di(borate), a white solid. It had m.p. 118-20°, b.p. 190°/0.6 mm. The essential details are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Alkyl borate (1M).	Diethanolaminic.	Ethanol in azeo- trope.	Yield of the di(borate).	% Found*.	
					Boron.	Nitrogen.
1.	Ethyl borate (7.6 g.)	8.2 g. (1.5M)	6.88 g. (2.87M)	8.40 g.	6.48	12.4
2.	Ethyl borate (8.9 g)	6.37 (1M)	5.40 (1.7M)	6.50	6.50	12.3
3.	Ethyl borate (4.24 g.)	9.14 (3M)	3.93 g. (2.95M)	3.30	6.49	12.3
4.	Isopropyl borate (8.12 g.)	4.51 (1M)	5.14 (1.98M)	5.07	6.50	12.4

* $C_{12}H_{27}O_6N_3B_2$ requires B, 6.53; N, 12.7%.

Reaction between Diethanolamine and Boric Acid (Molar Ratio 1:1).—A mixture of diethanolamine (14.3 g., 1M) and boric acid (8.44 g., 1M) was refluxed for 5 hours at a bath temperature of 180-90°. Water (4.9 g.) was then slowly distilled. A colorless, heavy liquid (17.76 g.) was obtained which, on drying at 50°/1 mm for 4 hours, changed to diethanolamine hydrogen borate (17.7 g., m.p. 76°), a white glassy compound, highly susceptible to hydrolysis. (Found: B, 8.1; N, 10.4. $C_4H_{10}O_5NB$ requires B, 8.25; N, 10.7%).

Reaction of Diethanolamine with Boric Acid and Cyclohexanol (Molar Ratio 1:1:1).—On refluxing a mixture of diethanolamine (4.41 g., 1M), boric acid (2.6 g., 1M), and cyclohexanol (4.2 g., 1M) in xylene (40 ml) for 2 hours and then fractionating through a 6' column, a colorless semisolid, immiscible in xylene, was obtained. Excess of xylene was decanted and the compound was dried at 75-80°/1 mm for 3 hours to yield diethanolamine hydrogen borate (5.4 g.), m. p. 75-78°. (Found: B, 8.16; N, 10.3%).

Reaction among diethanolamine, boric acid, and benzyl alcohol, in molar ratio 1:1:1 furnished diethanolamine hydrogen borate as above.

Reaction of Diethanolamine and Boric Acid with Phenol (Molar Ratio 1:1:1).—A mixture of diethanolamine (7.46 g., 1M), boric acid (4.40 g., 1M), and phenol (6.68 g., 1M) in xylene (50ml) was refluxed for 3 hours and then fractionated. After distilling water and xylene, a colorless heavy liquid, immiscible in xylene, was obtained which after some time changed into a white solid. Excess of xylene was decanted and phenyl diethanolamine borate (14 g., m. p. 125°), thus obtained, was dried at 60°/0.5 mm for 4 hours. It was further purified by sublimation at 210°/0.1 mm. (Found: B, 5.27; N, 6.4. $C_{10}H_{14}O_5NB$ requires B, 5.22; N, 6.7%).

Reaction between Triethanolamine and Ethyl Borate (Molar Ratio 1:1).—Triethanolamine (5.1 g., 1 *M*) was mixed with ethyl borate (5.10 g., 1 *M*) in benzene (40 g.). A white compound, insoluble in benzene, was precipitated instantaneously with evolution of much heat. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours, but boroxazolidine, thus formed, did not go in solution. On fractionation, 4.7g. of ethanol (3 moles require 4.82 g.) was obtained in the azeotropic. Excess of benzene was decanted and the compound, m. p. 232-34°, was dried at 40°/1 mm for 2 hours. It was further purified by sublimation at 220°/0.01 mm. (Found: B, 6.78; N, 8.6; M.W., 153. Calc. for $C_6H_{12}O_3NB$: B, 6.88; N, 8.9%; M.W., 157).

One of the authors (G. S.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.

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Received December 26, 1961.